

Isolation and Characterization of Community-Acquired *Staphylococcus aureus* collected from different Slum Populations of Midnapore Town

Tiyasha Mishra¹, Priyanka Jana², Ahana C³

1. Department of Biochemistry, Vidyasagar University, W.B-721102
2. Department of Biotechnology, Vidyasagar University, W.B-721102
3. Department of Biosciences and Biomedical Engineering, IIT Indore, M.P- 452020

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ABSTRACT

Antibiotic resistance is increasing rapidly, like a tsunami. *Staphylococcus aureus* is a prevalent pathogen causing both nosocomial and community-acquired infections worldwide. *Staphylococcus aureus* is one of the pathogenic bacteria that are rapidly evaluating themselves to become resistant to several antibiotics. Resistance against methicillin can be said as methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA). MRSA is divided into two subgroups: the hospital-associated MRSA (HA-MRSA) and community-associated MRSA (CA-MRSA). Community-acquired *Staphylococcus aureus* is a major pathogen responsible for skin and soft tissue infections (SSTIs). We surveyed the slum areas of Midnapore town and collected samples from infected individuals. After isolation of bacteria through MSA media, 15 bacteria were isolated. Molecular identification was done by PCR using species-specific 16S rRNA gene primer pairs, and finally, 15 isolates were found to be positive as *S. aureus*. Antibiotic sensitivity tests were performed on the confirmed MRSA isolates. Most of the bacterial samples are methicillin and nalidixic acid resistant. 100% bacteria show catalase positive, where all of them are oxidase negative. 87% bacterial samples can ferment glucose, and 67% are positive for sucrose fermentation. 80% bacterial samples are urease positive, and 53% can hydrolyse starch. 60% samples show Simmons citrate positive. All isolated samples are biofilm-producing bacteria isolated in Congo red agar medium. 40% are high, 47% are moderate, and 13% are low biofilm-producing bacteria.

Keywords: *Staphylococcus aureus*, SSTIs, MRSA, MDR, Biofilm, 16 S rRNA

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1. Introduction

Antibiotic use has significantly impacted bacterial life, and an estimated 100,000 tons of antibiotics are produced annually worldwide (Basak et al., 2016). Over the past few decades, infections with community-acquired methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (CA-MRSA) have been reported all over the world (Zetola et al., 2005). The establishment of a community pathogen depends on its capacity to flourish in many environments and efficiently interact with its host. The *Staphylococcus aureus* is one of the most effective and adaptable human infections. This bacterium is not hazardous because it is a part of the human microbiota and can live for a long time without harming people's health (Gelatt et al., 2009). A Gram-positive bacterium called *Staphylococcus aureus* is present in the skin, intestines, throat, and nasal passages. When the skin barrier is weakened, it can lead to infection (Sunagar et al., 2016). *Staphylococcus aureus's* ability to produce biofilms and express a variety of virulence factors accounts for its success as a pathogen. These characteristics enable the development of persistent and recurrent infections by helping *Staphylococcus aureus* not only invade the body but also withstand antimicrobials and host defence mechanisms (Bukharie, 2010). Treatment for human *Staphylococcus aureus* infections fails due to the establishment and spread of MRSA isolates, increasing mortality and morbidity (Shaw and Majumdar, 2021). Currently recognized as distinct clonal entities, CA-MRSA strains are distinct from typical hospital-acquired MRSA (HA-MRSA) infections. Despite having notable differences in epidemiology, microbiologic characteristics, clinical aspects of infection, and therapeutic approaches, CA-MRSA and HA-MRSA are both, by definition resistant to methicillin (and all beta-lactam antibiotics). *Staphylococcal* cassette chromosome (SCCmec) types IV or V and Panton-Valentine leucocidin (*pvl*) genes are present in CA-MRSA strains, which infect healthy young people who have never had any prior healthcare contact and are tolerant to the majority of non- β -lactam antibiotics (Otter and French, 2012). Infection with CA-MRSA is frequently linked to invasive infections that require intensive care and hospitalization in addition to skin/soft tissue infections (SSTIs) (Mongkolrattanothai et al., 2003). MRSA, or methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus*, got its name because this bacterium became resistant to oxacillin, which is the US counterpart of methicillin (Gajdács, 2019). Community-associated methicillin-susceptible *S aureus* (CA-MSSA) is the most common cause of SSTIs in North America, Latin America, and Europe (Moet et al., 2007), but clinicians and researchers are especially worried about CA-MRSA. Infections with CA-MRSA in children who had no known risk factors started to appear in the 1990s (Mera et al., 2011). The possibility of serious illness brought on

by CA-MRSA is of special concern to researchers. Numerous institutions have discussed their experiences with paediatric infections caused by community-acquired *Staphylococcus aureus* (CA-SA). Regardless of antibiotic resistance, severe illness has been associated with *Staphylococcus aureus* that is positive for Panton-Valentine leukocidin (Thomas et al., 2009). The presence of pathogenic *Staphylococcus aureus* in the studied area is suggested by the identification of the *pvl* gene in community-acquired *Staphylococcus aureus*. For high-level multidrug-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* infections, such as MRSA, the current research is crucial and instructive (Karmakar et al., 2018). To assess the probability of issues for patients with *Staphylococcus aureus* bacteraemia, a risk-scoring system was created (Fowler et al., 2003). The score takes into account individual risk factors such as a prolonged fever beyond 72 hours, a positive follow-up blood culture between 48 and 96 hours, cutaneous symptoms indicating an acute systemic infection, and an illness acquired in the community (Gomes et al., 2013). Although less frequent than skin infections, CA-MRSA strains can cause invasive, rapidly spreading, and sometimes fatal infections such as necrotizing fasciitis, severe sepsis, and necrotizing pneumonia (Kale and Dhawan, 2016). Cervical lymphadenitis, otitis externa, otitis media with otorrhea, acute mastoiditis, and retropharyngeal abscess are among the more prevalent CA-MRSA infections. As in normal Lemierre's syndrome, jugular vein thrombosis may accompany retropharyngeal abscesses that progress into the mediastinum (Bassetti et al., 2009).

1.1. Definition of CA-MRSA

A standardised definition of CA-MRSA was designed by the US Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) Active Bacterial Core surveillance (ABCs) sites in 2000 (Dakota, 1999). This defines CA-MRSA infections as an MRSA infection in an individual who has had: (i) a positive culture from anybody site within 48 h of admission to a hospital; (ii) no history of hospitalisation, surgery or residency in a long-term care facility within the past year; (iii) no current indwelling percutaneous devices or indwelling catheters; and (iv) no prior positive culture for MRSA. As a prior positive culture with CA-MRSA has been identified as an important risk factor for CA-MRSA, it has been suggested to omit or modify the fourth criterion of the CDC definition to avoid CA-MRSA being misclassified as a healthcare-associated (HA) infection (Harriman, 2004).

1.2. Global epidemiology of CA-MRSA

Globally, the prevalence of CA-MRSA varies. Different nations have varying rates of MRSA among community-acquired *Staphylococcus aureus* infections (Vourti et al., 2009; Vainio et al., 2011; Elston and Barlow, 2009; Olesevich and Kennedy, 2007; Immergluck, 2007). Compared to adults, children have a higher prevalence. While outbreaks in the USA, Taiwan, Canada, and Australia have been more widespread, CA-MRSA-infected cases have only been documented in small outbreaks or case series in many other countries (Deleo et al., 2010; David and Daum, 2010; Otter and French, 2010; Nimmo and Coombs, 2008; Hung and Chen, 2011). In each of these nations, endemic CA-MRSA infection has spread to certain demographic groups. For instance, the prevalence of CA-MRSA infections in children in Taiwan rose dramatically from 9.8% in 1999–2000 to 56% in 2004–2005 (Hirvonen et al., 2012). However, the prevalence of CA-MRSA infections, particularly invasive ones, has not been spatially uniform within nations, such as the USA (Bartels et al., 2010). Although low, CA-MRSA prevalence is rising in Europe (Grundmann et al., 2010). Although retrospective research found occurrences of CA-MRSA infection in the Netherlands in the late 1980s and Denmark in the early 1990s, European cases were first reported from France in 2002. The country with the highest prevalence of CA-MRSA to date is Greece, where PVL-positive strains are now a common cause of endemic HA infections in certain hospitals. In the Netherlands and Nordic nations, where HA-MRSA infection rates are still relatively low, CA-MRSA infection accounts for a significant portion of MRSA infections (Larsen et al., 2009; Söderquist and Berglund, 2008; Stam-Bolink et al., 2007; Urth et al., 2005; Song et al., 2011).

It is believed that CA-MRSA strains are regularly imported into these nations from endemic nations (Foster, 2019; Lowy, 1998;). Although there is a lack of information on the epidemiology of MRSA in poorer nations, there is worry that CA-MRSA could have disastrous effects if it spreads like wildfire in areas with limited resources. A prospective surveillance study was recently carried out in eight Asian nations between 2004 and 2006 (Otto, 2014). According to this study, MRSA was responsible for 25.5% of the 1463 isolates of CA *Staphylococcus aureus* infections; in Taiwan, the Philippines, Vietnam, and Sri Lanka, a rate of greater than 30% was seen (Tong et al., 2015).

1.3 Biofilm: The Survival Strategy of *Staphylococcus aureus*

Staphylococcus species, particularly *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Staphylococcus epidermidis*, are well-known for their ability to form biofilms, which are structured communities of bacterial

cells enclosed in a self-produced polymeric matrix and attached to surfaces. Biofilm formation is a critical virulence factor contributing to persistent infections, antibiotic resistance, and immune system evasion (Cerca et al., 2005; Boyce et al., 2005; Mahmood et al., 2010).

Biofilms formed by *Staphylococcus* are especially problematic in clinical settings, notably on indwelling medical devices such as catheters, prosthetic joints, and heart valves. These biofilms provide a protective niche that limits the penetration of antibiotics and shields bacteria from host immune responses, leading to chronic and relapsing infections [56].

Fig. 1: Five major phases of biofilm formation (Aiyer et al., 2018)

1.4 Antibiotic Resistance Profile of CA-MRSA:

Community-associated *Staphylococcus aureus* strains that exhibit methicillin resistance (CA-MRSA) possess resistance mechanisms primarily mediated by the *mecA* gene, which encodes an altered penicillin-binding protein (PBP2a) with low affinity for β -lactam antibiotics. This confers resistance to all β -lactam antibiotics, including penicillins and cephalosporins. Unlike hospital-associated MRSA (HA-MRSA), CA-MRSA often lacks multidrug resistance, but resistance profiles are evolving. While CA-MRSA strains were initially susceptible to several non- β -lactam antibiotics, increasing resistance has been observed (Thomas et al., 2009). Resistance to aminoglycosides (e.g., gentamicin, kanamycin, streptomycin) occurs through three primary mechanisms: aminoglycoside-modifying enzymes, target site (ribosomal) mutations, and active efflux pumps. CA-MRSA infections are commonly treated with non- β -lactam antibiotics such as clindamycin and trimethoprim-sulfamethoxazole (co-trimoxazole). Due to emerging resistance, newer broad-spectrum antibiotics have gained importance in CA-MRSA management. Linezolid, an oxazolidinone, is often used due to its oral bioavailability

and effectiveness. In rare cases, resistance to glycopeptides like vancomycin has been reported (VRSA) (Otto,2008).

1.5 Global study

The discovery of methicillin resistance in nosocomial *S. aureus* samples dates back to 1961 [Boyce JM et al. 2005]. Since then, methicillin-resistant *S. aureus* (MRSA) has proliferated in intensive care units and hospitals across the globe. 40–70% of *S. aureus* infections in intensive care units are caused by MRSA, making it one of the most prevalent sources of bacterial nosocomial infections at the moment [Mahmood K et al. 2010]. Before the initial reports of community-acquired MRSA, or CA-MRSA, in the 1980s, MRSA infections were mainly believed to be a hospital concern [Elston J W T & Barlow G D, 2009]. Since then, the epidemiology of these microorganisms has changed due to the identification of MRSA strains in the community known as HA-MRSA (Healthcare-Acquired), which have genetic and phenotypic traits different from hospital strains and cause infections in healthy individuals who have not been exposed to the typical risk factors. CA-MRSA strains were implicated in four pediatric deaths in Minnesota and North Dakota between 1997 and 1999. Deadly infections in youngsters in North Dakota and Minnesota were the main emphasis [Dakota N, 1999]. Children with invasive infections were the source of more CA-MSSA isolates (8.2%) than CA-MRSA isolates (4.4%) during a three-year monitoring of CA-SA infections at Texas Children's Hospital [Gomes R T et al. 2013]. Between 1999 and 2002, the percentage of community-acquired isolates increased from 41.7% to 66.6%. In each of these nations, CA-MRSA infection has spread to endemic levels among specific demographic groups [Bazzi A M, 2015]. For instance, the prevalence of CA-MRSA infections in children in Taiwan rose dramatically from 9.8% in 1999–2000 to 56% in 2004–2005 [Skov R et al. 2012]. A recent investigation of CA-MRSA pneumonia among hospitalized children in Hawaii found that MRSA-infected individuals were more likely to have pulmonary problems [Len K A et al. 2021]. A prospective cross-sectional, multi-center study of 591 clinical isolates from 66 hospitals in Argentina in 2009 revealed a significantly higher MRSA proportion among community-onset *S. aureus* infections than hospital-onset *S. aureus* infections (58% vs. 49%), particularly in children (62% vs. 43%) [Kale P & Dhawan, 2016]. The death rate may be 10 million per year globally by the year 2050 and will cost 100 trillion dollars, if proper actions are not taken to deal with the AMR [Shaw K & Majumdar S, 2021].

1.5.1 Study in India

A recent study found that, except Hong Kong, Indonesia (28% each), and South Korea (>70%), the frequency of methicillin-resistant *S. aureus* clinical isolates in India in the early 2010s (45%) is comparable to that reported in the other Asian countries (41.9% in Pakistan, 45.8% in China, 41% in Japan, 35.3% in Singapore, and 55.9% in Taiwan). In 1988, the incidence of HA-MRSA was as low as 6.9% in clinical samples from hospitals, but by the late 1990s, it had increased to 27%, 32%, 42.5%, and 47% in Mumbai, Vellore, Delhi, and Bengaluru, respectively. In both rural and urban areas, CA-MRSA infections have been reported in both healthy individuals and schoolchildren (Sunagar et al., 2016). The majority of hospital-acquired MRSA infections in India have been attributed to ST239-III. This typical hospital clone has gradually decreased in Indian hospitals in recent years, while community lineages like ST22-IV (EMRSA-15) and ST772-V have emerged [Rajan et al., 2015].

On the other hand, the prevalence of MRSA25 decreased in the countries that took some preventive action against AMR (antimicrobial resistance). Pathogens that are resistant to first-line antibiotics cause more than 50,000 neonatal deaths in India each year. AMR is expected to cause roughly 2 million fatalities in India by 2050, according to a paper by the Centre for Disease Dynamics, Economics & Policy [Shaw & Majumdar, 2021].

1.5.2 Study in West Bengal

Research conducted in 2014 at Medinipur Medical College in West Bengal revealed that 21.47% of HCWs were positive nasal carriers for *S. aureus*, with MRSA79 accounting for 30.7% of these cases. In a similar vein, Kulshrestha et al.'s 2019 study discovered that 11% of healthcare workers had positive MRSA colonization, and 95.3% were positive nasal carriers for *Staphylococcus aureus*. Out of 136 breast abscess pus samples, 124 *S. aureus* colonies were discovered in another study carried out at RG Kar Medical College and Hospital. Of the strains, 70 (56.5%) were MRSA. 34 of the 66 pus samples used in a study at a dentistry college in Kolkata had positive *S. aureus* cultures. Of the isolates, 14 (41.2%) had positive MRSA tests. A cross-sectional study on surgical site infections (SSI) was conducted over 3.5 years. *Staphylococcus aureus* was responsible for 34.93% of the reported 15.51% of SSI cases (1049). MRSA5 was found in 25.45% of *Staphylococcus aureus*. According to Amit et al.'s findings, 70% of MRSA were found during their examination at Midnapur Medical College and Hospital. Among 226 pus samples, 102 positive *S. aureus* colonizations were discovered in another study conducted by RG Kar Medical College and Hospital. 36 (35.3%) of the 102

Staphylococcus aureus were found to be MRSA. Prashant et al. analysed 395 CA MRSA samples and discovered 90 (22.7%) *Staphylococcus aureus*. Additionally, 80 MRSA isolates (20.2%) were found. [Majumdar S. & Shaw K., 2021]

2. EXPERIMENTAL DESIGN

3. METHODS AND MATERIALS

3.1 Collection of samples

A total of 20 non-repeat community strains of *S. aureus* were collected from human subjects of different slum areas (Table 1 and Fig. 3) of Midnapore town, West Bengal, India (Lat. 22°23'41.57''N to 22°26'22.02''N; Long. 87°17'23.65''E to 87°20'15.35''E). For sample collection, sterile swabs with rayon tips were used; for a moist wound, it was used directly, but for a dry wound, it was moistened with sterile saline so that it could increase the chance of recovery of the organism from the infected sites.

Table 1. No of collected samples from different slum areas of Midnapore town

Source of the isolates	Number of collected samples
Rangamati	10
Budge town	10

Fig.3 Study area

3.2. Isolation and identification of bacteria through MSA media:

All the samples were transferred into 2 gm% Luria broth (one for each specimen) and incubated at 37°C in a shaking incubator. After 16-18 hours, all the samples were inoculated onto a mannitol salt agar plate and incubated for 24-25 hours at 37°C [13]. All yellow pigmented colonies were inoculated into LB agar for culture preservation at 4°C. The resulting growth from respective plates of media was examined for colony characteristics and morphology (Karmakar et al., 2018).

Fig.4 Collection of samples. A: Samples collected from the superficial infected site. B: Collection of bacterial samples using sterile swab sticks with cotton tips. After the collection of samples, these sticks were dipped into sterile Luria-Bertani broth

3.3. DNA Extraction from Bacterial Culture Isolates

For the extraction of DNA from bacterial culture, the rapid boiling method was followed (Karmakar et al., 2018). In brief, 4 to 5 single colonies from an overnight-grown culture were inoculated in 200 L of sterile Milli-Q water and boiled at 99°C for 10 minutes. After centrifugation at 14000 rpm for 10 min, the supernatant was collected in a sterile microcentrifuge tube gently. The resultant template DNA was stored at -20°C, and 1 µL of each sample was used for PCR analysis.

3.4. Molecular Identification through PCR Amplification of 16S rRNA Gene

Phenotypically isolated and confirmed *S. aureus* isolates were further tested by PCR amplification assay using primer pairs for species-specific 16S rRNA gene. These primers amplified a 228 bp fragment from the 16S rRNA gene of these isolated *S. aureus* strains (Karmakar et al., 2018). The PCR procedure was carried out in a 25 µL PCR tube, and each of the reaction mixtures contained 5 µL Taq mixture; 2µL of forward primer; 2 µL of reverse primer; 1 µL of DNA; and 15.75 µL PCR grade water. The amplifications took place by the

process of PCR thermocycling in a thermal cycler (Eppendorf, Germany) commencing with an initial denaturation at 94°C for 2 minutes followed by 33 cycles, each consisting of denaturation at 94°C for 30 sec, annealing at 50°C for 30 sec, and polymerization at 72°C for 45 sec with a final extension at 72°C for 4 minutes. *S. aureus* ATCC 25923 was used as a positive control in this experiment.

3.5. Biochemical Characterizations of Genotypically Confirmed *Staphylococcus aureus*

3.5.1. Gram staining

Take a clean, clear, grease-free glass slide and transfer a small amount of the colony and suspend it with a water drop. Spread the suspension with the sterile inoculating loop to prepare a thin smear. Let the smear air dry and fix it by passing it over the flame. Flood the crystal violet solution over the fixed smear. After 30 – 60 seconds, flood the Gram's Iodine solution over the smear. After 30 – 60 seconds, rinse with gentle running water and decolourizer, passing on the smear. Gently rinse with distilled water and safranin as a counterstain. The smear is rinsed with water and air dried for analysis (Karmakar et al., 2016).

3.5.2. Catalase test

The catalase test detects the presence of the enzyme catalase in bacteria. A small amount of bacterial colony is placed on a clear, grease-free glass slide, and a drop of 30% hydrogen peroxide is added. Immediate bubbling indicated a positive result, showing oxygen release due to catalase activity (Karmakar et al., 2016).

3.5.3. Oxidase test

The oxidase test detects the presence of cytochrome c oxidase enzyme in bacteria. A colony is rubbed onto Kovacs's reagent-soaked filter paper. A positive result showed a dark purple color within 10–30 seconds (Ali et al., 2023).

3.5.4. Glucose fermentation

5 ml of nutrient broth supplemented with 1% glucose and phenol red as a pH indicator was prepared. A Durham tube was completely submerged in each test tube. The medium was then sterilized and subsequently inoculated with a fresh pure bacterial culture using a sterile inoculation loop. The inoculated tubes were incubated at 37°C for 18 to 24 hours (Ali et al., 2023).

3.5.5 Sucrose fermentation

5 ml of nutrient broth supplemented with 1% sucrose and phenol red as a pH indicator was prepared. A Durham tube was completely submerged in each test tube. The medium was then sterilized and subsequently inoculated with a fresh pure bacterial culture using a sterile inoculation loop. The inoculated tubes were incubated at 37°C for 18 to 24 hours (Ali et al., 2023).

3.5.6. Urease test

The urease test detects the presence of the urease enzyme, which breaks down urea into ammonia and carbon dioxide. For performing this test, the nutrient media are prepared and sterilized in an autoclave. pH indicator phenol red is also sterilized, but urea is not autoclaved to avoid breakdown of urea. After sterilization, phenol red and 2 % urea are mixed with the nutrient media. The medium is dispensed into tubes and set in a position to obtain agar slants. A loopful of a well-isolated colony is taken with an inoculating loop and inoculated on the agar slants. The tubes are then incubated with loosened caps at 37°C for 24 – 48 hours (Xu et al., 2023).

3.5.7. Starch hydrolysis

The starch hydrolysis test, also known as the amylase test. 2% starch agar media is prepared and sterilized in an autoclave. When the medium is cooled to around 40 to 45°C, in a sterile petri dish, dispense about 20 to 25 mL of the medium and let it solidify. Using a sterile inoculating loop, pick up the sample bacteria from several fresh colonies (of about 18 to 20 hours) and streak the bacteria in the form of short and thick straight lines over the surface of the bacteria. Incubate at 37°C for at least 48 hours. Following incubation, add a few drops of iodine solution directly over the colonies and observe for the formation of a clear halo around the colonies (Ali et al., 2023).

3.5.8. Simmons' citrate test

Simmons' citrate test is performed to determine the ability of bacteria to utilize citrate as the sole carbon source. Simmon's citrate agar slant is inoculated with an overnight bacterial culture and incubated at 37°C for 24–48 hours. A positive result is indicated by visible growth and a blue color change, while a negative result shows no growth and the medium remains green (Parking et al., 2019).

3.6 Biofilm assay

3.6.1. Qualitative test

The medium is composed of Brain Heart Infusion broth (37 gm/L), sucrose (5 gm/L), agar (15 gm/L), and Congo red dye (0.8 gm/L). Congo red stain was prepared as a concentrated aqueous solution and autoclaved at 121°C for 15 minutes. Then it was added to autoclaved Brain Heart Infusion agar with sucrose at 55 °C. Plates were inoculated with the test organism and incubated at 37°C for 24 to 48 hours aerobically. Black colonies with a dry crystalline consistency indicated biofilm production (Karmakar et al., 2018).

3.6.2. Quantitative test

The isolated bacteria were grown in 3 ml of Luria broth overnight. Ten 5 ml of the overnight culture was added to 500 ml of sterile LB in test tubes to make a dilution of 1:100. The Test tubes were kept standing statically for 24 hours, and after that, the test tubes were rinsed vigorously with distilled water to remove all non-adherent cells. Further, 600 ml of 0.1% (w/v) crystal violet was added and incubated for 30 minutes. Test tubes were then rinsed vigorously with distilled water. 1 ml DMSO was added to it, followed by vortexing. After incubation for 10 minutes optical density was measured at 570 nm. Each assay was performed in triplicate. The mean values of optical densities obtained were categorized into three classes such that the strains with $OD_{570} < 0.2$, $0.2 \leq OD_{570} \leq 1.0$, and $OD_{570} > 1.0$ were defined as biofilm non-formers and biofilm formers of weak level and strong level, respectively (Singh et al., 2017).

3.6.3. Antibiotic Susceptibility Profile of Isolated *S. aureus*

The antibiotic susceptibility pattern of *S. aureus* isolates was determined by the disk diffusion method using commercial antibiotic disks procured from Hi Media, Mumbai [63]. The antibiotic disks used were as follows: amikacin (10 mg), nalidixic acid (30mg), cefoxitin (30mg), Vancomycin (10mg), methicillin (10 mg), co-trimoxazole (25 mg), and Ciprofloxacin (5 mg). Antibiotic susceptibility of those isolates was evaluated according to the Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute (CLSI) (Bauer et al., 1966).

4. RESULT

4.1. Collected samples characterization

Table2. Characterization of collected samples according to source of collection, sex, and age group

Sex	Superficial infected sites		Nasal cavity	
	Age ≤ 30 years	Age > 30 years	Age ≤ 30 years	Age > 30 years
Male	1	2	3	3
Female	3	1	4	3
Total number of samples	4	3	7	6

The percentage is presented in parenthesis

4.2. Isolation and identification of *Staphylococcus aureus* through MSA media

All samples are isolated in MSA media for 18 – 24 hours, and 15 samples show a positive result.

Table 3. Results of isolated samples.

Number of samples	Positive (%)	Negative (%)
20	15 (75)	5 (25)

The percentage is presented in parenthesis

Fig5: Isolation and identification of *Staphylococcus aureus* by Mannitol salt agar (MSA) A-B. Mannitol fermenting strains produce a yellow color in red MSA media, indicating a positive result.

4.3. Colony characterization by pigment analysis

Table 4. Characterization of bacterial isolates by pigment analysis

Number of samples	White (%)	Creamy (%)	Yellow (%)
15	5 (33)	3 (20)	7 (47)

The percentage is presented in parenthesis

4.4. Molecular identification of *Staphylococcus aureus* through PCR of species-specific 16S rRNA gene

Table 5. Molecular identification through PCR of species-specific 16s rRNA gene.

Number of samples	Positive (%)	Negative (%)
15	15 (100)	0 (0)

The percentage is presented in parenthesis

4.5. Biochemical Characterizations of Genotypically Confirmed *Staphylococcus aureus*

4.5.1. Gram staining

Gram-positive bacteria appear violet, and gram-negative bacteria appear pink or red. After Gram staining, all 15 bacterial samples are Gram-positive concinnated in parenthesis

Table 6. Gram staining result

Number of samples	Positive (%)	Negative (%)
15	15 (100)	0 (0)

The percentage is presented in parenthesis

Fig.6. Gram staining: Appearing violet color indicating gram-positive bacteria

4.5.2. Catalase test

The positive test is demonstrated by the immediate appearance of bubbles. A negative test is represented by no bubbles or a few bubbles after 20 s.

Table 7. Catalase test results

Number of samples	Positive (%)	Negative (%)
15	15 (100)	0 (0)

The percentage is presented in parenthesis

Fig.7. Catalase test: Formation of bubbles indicating a positive result

4.5.3. Oxidase test

Development of purple to deep blue colour indicates Oxidase positive. No development of purple to deep blue indicates Oxidase negative.

Table 8. Oxidase test results

Number of samples	Positive (%)	Negative (%)
15	0 (0)	15 (100)

The percentage is presented in parenthesis

Fig.8. Oxidase: Bacterial smear becomes colorless, indicating a negative result

4.5.4. Glucose fermentation

Positive fermentation is denoted by the colour change of the media from reddish-orange to yellow. Negative fermentation is denoted by no colour change of the medium. Gas production is indicated by the formation of an air bubble in Durham’s tube.

Table 9. Glucose fermentation results

Number of samples	Positive (%)	Negative (%)	Gas formation (%)
15	13 (87)	2 (13)	0(0)

The percentage is presented in parenthesis

Fig.9. Glucose fermentation test: The Media turns yellow, indicating a positive result.

4.5.5. Sucrose fermentation

Positive fermentation is denoted by the colour change of the media from reddish-orange to yellow. Negative fermentation is denoted by no colour change of the medium. Gas production is indicated by the formation of an air bubble in Durham’s tube.

Table10. Sucrose fermentation results

Number of samples	Positive (%)	Negative (%)	Gas formation (%)
15	10(67)	5 (33)	0(0)

The percentage is presented in parenthesis

Fig.10. Sucrose fermentation test: The media turns yellow, indicating a positive result.

4.5.6. Urease test

A positive test is demonstrated by an intense magenta to bright pink colour in 24 - 48 hours. A negative test shows no colour change.

Table 11. Urease test results

Number of samples	Positive (%)	Negative (%)
15	12 (80)	3 (20)

The percentage is presented in parenthesis

Fig.11. Urease Test: Positive results indicated by bright fuchsia colour throughout the slant.

4.5.7. Starch hydrolysis

A positive result is indicated by the formation of a clear zone around the colonies and the development of dark blue surrounding medium after the addition of Gram's Iodine. A negative result is indicated by no clear zone around the colonies.

Table12. Starch hydrolysis results

Number of samples	Positive (%)	Negative (%)
15	8 (53)	7 (37)

The percentage is presented in parenthesis

Fig.12. Starch hydrolysis: A clear zone indicating Starch hydrolysis positive result

4.5.8. Simmons' citrate test

A positive result is indicated by the medium changing from green to a bright blue. Negative result indicated by the colour of the medium remains unchanged(green).

Table 13. Simmons citrate test results

Number of samples	Positive (%)	Negative (%)
15	9 (60)	6 (40)

The percentage is presented in parenthesis

Fig. 14 Simmons' citrate test: Bright blue color indicating positive result

4.6 Biofilm assay

4.6.1 Qualitative test

The Congo red agar (CRA) test is a qualitative method used to detect biofilm production by bacteria. Colonies that appear black, dry, and crystalline are generally considered positive for biofilm production. Pink or red colonies are typically considered negative for biofilm formation.

Table 14. Qualitative result of biofilm assay by using CRA media.

Number of samples	Positive (%)	Negative (%)
15	15(100)	0 (0)

The percentage is presented in parenthesis

Fig. 15 Congo red agar: Black regions indicate biofilm-positive result

4.6.2 Quantitative test

The crystal violet assay is a common method for quantifying biofilm formation. It involves staining the biofilm with crystal violet dye, which binds to the extracellular polymeric substance (EPS) and cells within the biofilm.

Table 15.1. Grade of biofilm based on OD value (Singh et al., 2017)

Average OD range	Biofilm grade
<0.238	Non former
≥ 0.238 but ≤ 0.477	Low biofilm former
≥ 0.477 but ≤ 0.954	Moderate biofilm former
≥ 0.954	High biofilm former

The percentage is presented in parenthesis

Table 15.2. Quantitative result of biofilm assay by using crystal violet.

Number of samples	High intensity (%)	Moderate intensity (%)	Low intensity (%)
15	6 (40)	7 (47)	2 (13)

The percentage is presented in parenthesis

Fig.16 Biofilm test: Blue colour adherence indicating a biofilm positive result.

4.6.3 Antibiotic susceptibility test

If an antibiotic stops the bacteria from growing or kills the bacteria, there will be an area around the disk where the bacteria have not grown enough to be visible. This is called a zone of inhibition. If any zone of inhibition is not produced around the antibiotic, then it is called a resistance strain.

Table16. Antibiotic susceptibility assay

Antibiotic	Disc concentration	Resistance (%)	Sensitive (%)
Methicillin (MFT)	5 mcg	12 (80)	3 (20)
Cefoxitin (CX)	30 mcg	12 (80)	3 (20)
Amikacin (AK)	30 mcg	11 (73)	4 (27)
Nalidixic acid (NA)	30 mcg	13 (86)	2 (14)
Vancomycin (VA)	10 mcg	5 (33)	10 (67)

The percentage is presented in parenthesis

5. DISCUSSIONS

The current study reflects the elevated level of multidrug-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* infections in the community. The major features that emerge in this initial study are that the incidence of MRSA infections is lower than in other Indian studies, probably because of the rural background of the population and lower population density. Causes of the emergence of drug resistance in *Staphylococcus aureus* may include inactivation of β -lactamase, glycopeptide access inhibition, reduced drug permeability into the bacterial cell, alteration of DNA gyrase, Cell wall thickening, etc. Moreover, the gene responsible for drug resistance, according to the study, may be transferred horizontally from one bacterium to another. The establishment of an Infection control program with documented Antibiotic policy will help in keeping rates of emergence of resistant organisms low in this region and may also help in arresting the spread of infection. In our study, we perform many types of experiments, such as PCR for a confirmation test by using species-specific primers. 15 bacteria are isolated, which are *Staphylococcus aureus* strain. Many biochemical assays are also used for the characterization of the bacteria. Gram-positive bacteria appear violet in color. The catalase positive test is demonstrated by the immediate appearance of bubbles. A negative test is represented by no bubbles or a few bubbles after 20 s. The development of purple to deep blue colour indicates Oxidase positive. No development of purple to deep blue indicates Oxidase negative. Positive fermentation of glucose and sucrose is denoted by the colour change of the media from reddish-orange to yellow. Urease positive test is demonstrated by an intense magenta to bright pink colour in 24 - 48 hours. A negative test shows no colour change. A

positive starch hydrolysis result is indicated by the formation of a clear zone around the colonies and the development of dark blue surrounding medium after the addition of Gram's Iodine. Simmons citrate Positive result is indicated by the colour of the medium changes from green to bright blue. Colonies that appear black, dry, and crystalline in CRA media are generally considered positive for biofilm production. No zone of inhibition formation indicates resistance of bacteria.

6. CONCLUSION

The present study emphasizes that the transmission of multidrug-resistant strains of *Staphylococcus aureus* poses a serious public health concern, often leading to more severe and persistent infections. Contributing factors include the misuse and overuse of antibiotics, failure to complete prescribed antibiotic courses, high population density, inadequate sanitation, and lack of awareness regarding hygiene and infection control. These issues collectively fuel the rising rate of community-acquired infections. This study not only highlights critical health and environmental concerns but also serves as a foundation for future research and public awareness initiatives aimed at curbing the spread of resistant *S. aureus*.

Abbreviations

MSCRAMM – Microbial Surface Components Recognizing Adhesive Matrix EPS – Extracellular Polymeric Substances

DMSO – Dimethyl sulfoxide DNA – Deoxyribonucleic Acid QS – Quorum Sensing

WHO – World Health Organization MSA – Mannitol Salt Agar

MRSA – Methicillin-Resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* MSSA – Methicillin-Sensitive *Staphylococcus*

aureus VISA – Vancomycin-Intermediate *Staphylococcus aureus* VSSA – Vancomycin-Susceptible *Staphylococcus aureus*

VRSA – Vancomycin-Resistant *Staphylococcus aureus*

CA-MRSA – Community Acquired-Methicillin-Resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* HA-MRSA –

Hospital Acquired-Methicillin Resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* PVL – Panton-Valentine Leukocidin

SCCmec – *Staphylococcal* cassette chromosome mec MIC – Minimum Inhibitory Concentrations

PCR – Polymerase Chain Reaction CRA – Congo Red Agar

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